

Ayurveda's Most important Upstambh Ahar

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Abstract—The human body as well as “diseases” are formed only by Ahaar. Wholesome and unwholesome foods are responsible for happiness and misery respectively. Ahar, nidra, brahmacharya are three significant pillars of Ayurveda. Ahar is the first and important pillar of ayurveda .

आ+ह- घय प्रत्यय (आहरणे) To take ,
भोजने “निराहारौ यताहारौ तन्मनस्कौ समाहितौ”

Which is taken by our body is ahar ,which proper food is taking, maintaining and improving our health. Ayurveda is science of life. Main aim of ayurveda .

स्वस्थस्य स्वास्थ्य रक्षणम्, आतुरस्य विकारप्रशमनं च | च.सू.30/26

The utility of Ayurveda is to help maintain the health of a healthy individual and cure diseases of a patient. Ahar plays an important role in achieving the target. It is one of the fundamental principles which gives health ,happiness and harmony along with nature. One should regularly take substances which are conducive to the preservation of good health and are able to avoid the illness. This type of diet is called a naturally healthy diet.

Index Terms—Component, formatting, style, styling, insert. (Key words)

I. Introduction

Ayurveda has a scientific approach in health management. The main aim of Ayurveda is to preserve the health of a healthy person and to treat the disease. The diet and regimen which is beneficial to the body and gives happiness to the mind. Lots of importance is given to the diet with regard to its processing, quality, quantity and so on. Àhàra, Swapna (Nidra) and Brahmacharya play an important role in the maintenance of “Swasthya” of an individual. Àhàra plays an important role in healthy, diseased and convalescent states. It is more important than the medicine itself. A wholesome diet is the prime cause for the growth and development of the body, on the contrary, an unwholesome diet causes several diseases. Acharya charaka stated that the ideal diet is that, which rebuilds the worn-out systems, nourishes dhàtus and maintains equilibrium of the body constituents. Irrational diet acts otherwise, producing disease. One should eat food, which is hot, unctuous, in due measure, after the digestion of previous food, and nonantagonistic in potency. It should be eaten in a hygienic place, provided with all accessories, neither too hurriedly, nor too leisurely, without talking or laughing with full concentration and having proper regard to oneself.

आहारसंभवं वस्तु रोगाश्चाहारसम्भवा|
हिताहितविशेषाच्च विशेषः सुखदुःखयो|| च.सू.28/45

Ahara i.e. diet is believed to be one of the Upastambha of life. Faulty diet results in disturbed functions of the body. That is the reason why while describing causative factors of diseases, dietary articles (apathya) have been given prime importance. Acharya Charak has stated that diet sustains life if taken with discipline in a proper manner. Ahara has a prime role in maintaining health and also in treating various disorders. Ayurveda emphasizes that the Àhàra is the nourisher of the body

elements; vital essence, vitality, complexion and other things, but its action is dependent on the proper function of Jatharagni. The Àhàra Dravyas comprising six Rasas, get transformed into three kinds of Vipaka (Madhura, Amla and Katu) by the action of Jatharagni. All living beings in the universe require food. Food is said to be the cause of stability for all living beings. There is nothing else except diet for sustaining the life of living beings. Complexion, clarity, good voice, longevity, astuteness, happiness, satisfaction, nourishment, strength and intellect are all conditioned by food. Diet supports the body constantly just like the house (is supported) by the pillars. A complete nutritional diet or wholesome food is responsible for the growth of the living beings while unwholesome food for the growth of diseases. Proper growth and maintenance of the body depends on a balanced diet.

बलमारोग्यमायुश्च प्राणाश्चाग्नौ प्रतिष्ठिता |
अन्नपानेन्धनैश्चाग्निर्ज्वलति व्येति चान्यथा ||च. सू.27/342

Strength, health, longevity and vital breath are dependent upon the power of digestion including metabolism. when supplied with fuel in the form of food and drinks, this power of digestion is sustained. it dwindles when deprived of it.

When food articles are taken in a quantity commensurate with the power of digestion, the latter is properly maintained resulting in the maintenance of health etc.

II. Conclusion

Food sustains the life of living beings. All living beings in the universe require food. complexion, good voice, satisfaction, nourishment, strength and intellect are all conditioned by food. Professional activities leading to happiness in this world, vedic rituals leading to abode in heaven and observance of truth, brahmacharya leading to salvation are all based on food.

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